

Using Contemporary Teaching Methods to Face Misconceptions Arising From the Formalism of Physics

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Abstract

This paper deals with an experimental intervention in teaching physics in senior high school. The aim is to investigate whether the proposed method using analogies, simulations, guided discovery, explorations, communication, and structured guided dialogues facilitates pupils to face their misconceptions and learning difficulties mainly created by the formalism of electromagnetism. In the introduction, some suggestions for the physics teaching where misconceptions of pupils are inevitable are presented. Then, an extended literature review is done which includes a review of theories of changing misconceptions, and a review of the use simulations and analogies in confronting misconceptions. The intervention presents step by step how the proposed method facilitates pupils to face misconceptions and learning difficulties created by the undefined forms and forms of infinite due to the formalism of electromagnetism. The study showed that the proposed method helps pupils face effectively their misconceptions.

Keywords: Conceptual Change, Contemporary Teaching Methods, Electric Charges, Electromagnetism, Lorentz Force, Pupils, Structured Guided Dialogues, Misconceptions.

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1. Introduction

The present work is a research which has as its main purpose to investigate a method of coping with misconceptions and learning difficulties of pupils created by the formalism of electromagnetism using analogies, simulations, guided discovery, explorations, communication, and structured guided dialogues.

Physics teaching is a discipline that deals with difficult abstract concepts. Therefore, some students encounter difficulties in understanding these concepts and may misunderstand some concepts when we teach physics in the classroom. According to Chi et al. (1991) [1], students have particular difficulty in comprehending physics concepts which have very few real-life referents and which incorporate invisible factors, forces operating at a distance, and complex abstractions. According to Furio & Guisasola (1998) [2], even advanced students have difficulty grasping non-intuitive, abstract concepts such as those found in electromagnetism. It is possible, therefore, the students to have misconceptions and learning difficulties when studying electromagnetism.

DiSessa (2000) [3] suggests that physics is best taught through experiments, labs, demonstrations, and visualizations which help the students understand physical phenomena conceptually. According to Concari et al. (2006) [4], being physics an experimental science, observation, measuring and theoretical speculations are processes that cannot be separated from the physical knowledge construction, even in the classroom. According to Snowman et al. (2015) [5], educators should consider stimulating the basic purposes of schooling curiosity, exploration, problem-solving, and communication.

The most effective learners should use multiple strategies to make sure that they check their comprehension. Thus, we need adequate didactic strategies to promote meaningful learning. While teaching in the frame of constructivism, it is necessary to take students' misconceptions and learning difficulties into consideration by using different teaching strategies and activities to support students to reconstruct their own cognitive models

and designing a learning environment where they can construct their ideas by themselves.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section (2) presents a literature review of the theoretical framework for changing misconceptions and the using of simulations, analogies, etc. in confronting pupils' misconceptions. Section (3) presents the method used for the study. Section (4) presents the findings of the research, Section (5) presents the discussion, and Section (6) presents the conclusions about the research.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Overview on Theories of Changing Misconceptions

Studies show the decisive influence of the pre-existing knowledge, either correct or wrong, in the learning process [6, 7]. Pre-existing knowledge could be described as the knowledge that learners have when they are introducing into a learning environment and is dynamically related to constructing new knowledge. Wrong pre-existing knowledge usually referred as misconceptions, preconceptions (pre-existing conceptions) or alternative conceptions by various researchers and theorists. As Brown (1992) [8] and Callinan (2016) [7] report, incorrect pre-existing knowledge in some learners is relatively stable and tends to resist change.

Eylon and Linn (1988) [9] consider that even after some years of teaching based on scientific theories, pupils oppose change, persisting in some of these incorrect and/or incomplete notions and they (re)appear to them as they solve problems.

Conceptual change is a popular, contemporary conception of meaningful learning. Conceptual change describes changes in conceptual frameworks (mental models or personal theories) that learners construct to comprehend phenomena. Conceptual change is a process of constructing and reorganizing personal conceptual models [10].

Conceptual change requires reconstructing pre-existing knowledge, providing pupils with a more

fruitful conceptual framework for particular environments [6, 11]. Some traditionally oriented approaches require that erroneous concepts are completely eliminated and replaced with other new concepts based on empirical data [12]. Several approaches to constructivism reject this replacement of knowledge and the transmission of ideas [13].

Vosniadou (2007) [11] argues that conceptual change is a learning process in which pupils' alternative conceptions transform (restructure) into the intended scientific conceptions. It activates learners to synthesize mental models starting from the existing explanatory frameworks. This is a gradual process that might be a step forward in advancing mental models. Chi and Roscoe (2002) [14] capture conceptual change as a "correction" of misconceptions. Vosniadou (2007) [11] also suggests that, for developing the learner meta-conceptual awareness, he or she could be encouraged to express his or her representations of phenomena so that they could be checked and compared to those of other learners will lead him or her to become conscious of what he knows and what he needs to learn.

When pre-existing knowledge has misconceptions, it is an obstacle to conceptual change. The misconception arises as a result of our personal interpretations of a concept. Pupils' misconceptions are an alternative way of interpreting natural phenomena [3, 7]. Misconceptions are generally fixed in pupil's mental models and are reluctant to transform [15, 16].

Therefore, misconceptions prevent learning. In order to deal with misconceptions, it is useful to understand how these are created. Necessary prerequisites for eliminating of misconceptions are learners' awareness of their views on the one hand and the lack of explanation of physical phenomena on the other [11].

Research has established that learners' misconceptions in science are very tenacious and that conventional teaching is notably ineffective in promoting conceptual change [7, 17, 18].

Chiappetta and Koballa (2006), [19] state that the teaching strategies and approaches that were effective in generating conceptual change had a common element, producing of *cognitive dissonance* (inconsistency or conflict). On the contrary, Duit et al. (2008) [6] state that there are several studies

available in the field of the scholarly concepts of learners, where they do not necessarily change their views on several teaching and learning approaches that structure the cognitive dissonance. In any case, cognitive conflicts are not generally a conceptual change [16, 20].

Cognitive dissonance is the psychological conflict between two or more incompatible beliefs simultaneously. Teaching and learning approaches designed to make cognitive dissonance typically employs *discrepant events* or data that contradict pupils' misconceptions, followed by opportunities to reflect upon their conceptions as they attempt to resolve the conflict [16, 19, 21]. Discrepant events might be demonstrations, simulations or phenomena, which need learners to explain or make predictions.

According to Limon (2001) [22], the success of the cognitive dissonance approach depends strongly on each pupil's ability to recognize and resolve the conflict. This means that several intellectually less able pupils may fail to recognize the conflict and some of those who do recognize it, perhaps not be able to resolve it [23].

Another method to confront misconceptions and learning difficulties of pupils is the socio-cognitive conflicts. In socio-constructivism, where learning is understood as a result of the interaction, collaboration-based activity, pairs or small groups, socio-cognitive conflicts are particularly appreciated. The learning environment interactions with other colleagues considering as the ideal source for promoting and resolving these conflicts, necessary to make sure that development can take place [24]. March (1991) [25] suggests that peer collaboration offers three cognitive benefits: *articulation*, *conflict*, and *co-construction*. For the sake of learners' joint activity, they need to articulate their opinions, predictions, and interpretations. Conflict sometimes arises from peer collaboration when learners disagree with each other in their interpretations or approaches to the task. When working on a task or solving a problem, learners co-construct shared knowledge and understanding by complementing and building on each other's ideas. [21, 26]

2.2. Use of Contemporary Didactic Approaches in Confronting Misconceptions

According to De Jong & van Joolingen (1998), [27], simulations are a promising tool for creating more realistic, experiential learning environments. Simulations offer a learning environment that is, in a way, unique. One of the basic advantages offered by simulations alone (unlike other computer learning tools) is the ability to learn through practice. This empirical way of learning is one of the keys to the theory of constructivism. Research has demonstrated the effectiveness of computer simulations in pupil learning.

According to Flick and Bell (2000), [28], the effectiveness of computer simulations is closely connected to the pedagogy through which they employed. According to Winn et al. (2006) [29], computer simulations have the potential to promote cognitive dissonance and conceptual change more effectively than direct experience.

According to Zacharia and Anderson (2003) [30], computer simulations used to offer discrepant events in conceptual learning because they are able to offer learners with an exploratory learning environment.

Computer simulations, comparing with other methods, have an additional advantage that learners can explore the simulation by changing the parameters and variables and visualizing immediately the consequences of their manipulations. Learners can interpret the underlying scientific conceptions of the program and compare them with their own conceptions.

How to engage young learners in complex physics thinking is a challenge, but simulations offer one intriguing way to engage learners in the study of abstract, complex physical phenomena. [3] According to McDermott (1990) [31], computer simulations have been proven effective against conceptual change in science. Also, the efficacy of computer simulations to promote cognitive dissonance and desired conceptual change is further supported by Trundle and Bell (2010) [32]. Moreover, a discrepancy between predictions and outcomes creates cognitive conflict in the pupils because the discrepant events provided contradicted the pupils' alternative conceptions and invoked cognitive conflict [33].

The analogy is a process of identifying similarities between two concepts. The familiar concept called the analogy and the unfamiliar science concept called

the target. Maxwell (1954) [34] strongly believed that it was possible to explain the electromagnetic phenomena using mechanical concepts. The use of analogies is usually considered as a strategy that is more constructive than disinformation [35].

Dilber and Duzgun (2008) [36] argue that analogical instruction helps pupils change their pre-existing conceptions or alternative conceptions with the scientific ones by activating their alternative conceptions, producing dissatisfaction and presenting a correct explanation which is both understandable and plausible. Analogies were helpful for learning abstract and complex concepts of electricity. When the analogical instruction used, it is highly probable that these cause much better understandings of scientific conception and elimination of alternative conceptions [36].

The learning goal of explorations and guided discovery didactic approaches are to motivate the learners to self-direct their learning process to learn how to apply knowledge and generally to develop higher-order thinking. The purpose of exploration is the learners to find out and comprehend concepts/knowledge embedded in the target domain. An exploration includes things captured by terms such as search, variation, risk-taking, experimentation, play, flexibility, discovery, and innovation [25].

De Jong and van Joolingen (1998) [27] presented research for the scientific discovery of learning using model simulations where the results are that pupils find it difficult to learn from simulations using discovery methods and they need more support to succeed. They also showed that pupils have difficulty in discovering learning processes, as they find it difficult to declare or make assumptions that lead to appropriated experiments.

In addition, pupils do not easily adapt their assumption based on the data they collect. Pupils look for and find results to explain their hypotheses. To explain these difficulties, de Jong and van Joolingen (1998) [27] presented a survey suggesting ways to face these difficulties. One of their conclusions is that more information and teaching support is necessary as pupils involved in the simulation.

Thus, guided discovery is used to confront these difficulties. The main purpose of the guided

discovery method is to lead learners to discover domain concepts with various learning facilities such as simulation, demonstration environments, and so on (Mayer, 2004) [37], as well as built-in guidance activities with simulations, such as exercises, questions, or even games, help pupils learn from the simulation [27].

In the present study, taking into account all the above, the methods of analogies, simulations, guided discovery, explorations, communication, and structured guided dialogues were used to address misconceptions arising from the formalism of electromagnetism. In the field of electromagnetism, the pupils' learning difficulties studied by various researchers. The misconceptions and learning difficulties of pupils created in comprehending the interaction between electrical charges and magnetic fields documented by Maloney (1985), [38], and Bagno and Eylon (1997) [39]. They support that pupils have difficulty in deciding on the direction of the Lorentz force and have the following misconceptions:

- a) Pupils consider that the magnetic poles exert forces on electric charges in the plane of the charged particle and magnet, regardless of whether the charge was moving or not.
- b) A constant magnetic field changes the speed (magnitude of velocity) of a charged particle which moves in it.
- c) Other misconceptions that need to be considered in this article are the following:
- d) Pupils consider that the magnetic poles exert forces on neutral electric charges ($q = 0$) in the plane of the uncharged particle (e.g., neutrino) and magnet, regardless of whether the charge was moving or not.
- e) Pupils have misconceptions and learning difficulties in cases of (a) $v = 0$ and $q = 0$, (b) $v = 0$ and $q \neq 0$, and (c) $v \neq 0$ and $q = 0$, when they calculate the radius and period of the circular orbit of a particle (charged or neutral charged), when it moves or not, perpendicular to a uniform magnetic field.

Taking into account the learning difficulties and misconceptions that recorded, as well as the

difficulties that are possibly caused by the formalism of physics, was designed an activity based on the theory of socio-constructivism [40] where pupils construct their own knowledge by working in an interactive simulated environment and collaboration.

3. Methods

3.1. Research hypotheses

The present work is a phenomenological research and its study design is iterative and flexible. The general hypothesis of the research was that the proposed method using analogies, simulations, guided discovery, explorations, communication, and structured guided dialogues helps pupils in confronting the following misconceptions and learning difficulties:

- a) The pupils consider that the magnetic poles exert forces on electric charges in the plane of the charged particle and magnet, regardless of whether the charge was moving or not;
- b) A constant magnetic field changes the speed (magnitude of velocity) of a charged particle which moves in it;
- c) As well as the following misconceptions and learning difficulties created by the formalism of electromagnetism:
- d) The pupils consider that the magnetic poles exert forces on neutral electric charges ($q = 0$) in the plane of the uncharged particle (e.g., neutrino) and magnet, regardless of whether the charge was moving or not;
- e) Pupils have misconceptions and learning difficulties in cases of (a) $v = 0$ and $q = 0$, (b) $v = 0$ and $q \neq 0$, and (c) $v \neq 0$ and $q = 0$, when they calculate the radius and period of a particle's circular orbit (charged or neutral charged), when it moves or not, perpendicular to a uniform magnetic field;

Other hypotheses are that the proposed method helps pupils:

- a) calculate physics quantities and correctly use the rule of the three fingers of the right hand to predict the particle motion;
- b) comprehend their errors and revise their views;

- c) be able to explain their choices;
- d) accept that formulas restrictions are required to avoid undefined and infinite forms;

3.2. Participants

The research conducted at the 4th Unified Lyceum (Senior High School) of Galatsi, Athens, Greece. Twelve sixteen-year-old pupils participated in the research. The small amount of pupils is due to the small amount of the school computer laboratory. Seven pupils were males and five females. Half of the pupils have had high performance levels in physics lessons, while the other halves have had poor performance levels in the same lessons. In the case of pupils' co-operation, the groups consisted of two pupils (dyads), one of whom has had a high performance level in physics lessons, while the other has had a poor performance level in the same lessons.

3.3. Educational Material

Taking into account the misconceptions and learning difficulties recorded in the international literature, as well as the difficulties caused by the formalism of physics, designed an activity based on the theory of constructivism and socio-constructivism, where pupils construct their own knowledge by working in an interactive simulated environment and collaboration. Activities carried out by pupils and they completed the worksheets. The module taught to pupils through the activity is the charged particle motion with constant speed v perpendicular to a uniform magnetic field.

The simulation software used is Interactive Physics™ [41] and the simulation method used is the model use.

3.4. Questionnaires

For the study, the mixed method was used for data analysis, quantitative and qualitative. For the qualitative data quota sampling was used. As tools for collect data have been used the observation of pupils' work during the experiment, worksheets for quantitative and qualitative data, and observations about the changing beliefs of pupils through the structured guided dialog (in-depth interview) by the

instructor as it will be described below.

3.5. Experimental Procedure

Teaching took place without preparation for the lesson. Pupils, in order to handle the interactive part of the simulation, were taught through the worksheet and demonstrated the handling of the simulation.

The experimental process lasted two teaching hours. The pupils were given the worksheet where they were asked the following:

1. See the below video (Figure (1)) linking the moon's circular motion around the earth with that of charged particle motion with a constant speed v perpendicular to a uniform magnetic field, and explore similarities and differences. Can we use the same formulas of mechanics in electromagnetism?

The moon orbits the earth with a constant speed v

Planetario di Milano

A charged particle is moving with a constant speed v perpendicular to a uniform magnetic field

Press the "Start video" button, compare the two motions, and answer the questions below.

Start video
Stop video

Figure 1. Pupils explore similarities and differences between the two motions.

2. Compose the below formulas that you have learned in the section of the uniform circular motion of an object in mechanics:

$$F_k = m \cdot \frac{v^2}{R} \quad (1), \quad v = \omega \cdot R \quad (2), \quad \text{and} \quad \omega = \frac{2\pi}{T} \quad (3)$$

and the below formula for calculating the Lorentz force that exerts the magnetic field on the charged particle:

$$F_L = B \cdot v \cdot |q| \quad (4)$$

Extract the formulas for calculating the radius and

period as a form with parameters of B, v, q, and m.

3. Calculate the radius and period for different values of the parameters v and q and predict the particle motion in the magnetic field.
4. Discuss in groups to exchange results, experiences, and findings, and make corrections if it is proper.
5. Experiment with the simulation, see the particle motions and record the radius and period values. Justify the differences between your predictions and results and findings. Write down the acceptable values on the worksheet.
6. Discuss in groups to exchange results, experiences, and findings, and make corrections if it is proper. Explain your possible changes you made through negotiation.
7. Set restrictions of formulas you have calculated on the values that the parameters can take.
8. Discuss your last results through a guided dialogue with the instructor.
9. Write down your explanations about your possible corrections on the worksheet (why have you made any corrections?)

In Stage 1 of the activity, pupils associate the pre-existing knowledge they have gained from the study of an object moving in uniform circular motion in mechanics, with the new knowledge of a charged particle moving with a constant velocity v perpendicular to a uniform magnetic field (analogy). In this stage, the pupils worked individually.

In Stage 2 of the activity, the pupils extracted the formulas with parameters B, v, q, and m for calculating the radius and period.

In Stage 3 of the activity, Table (1) was given to the participants and they were asked to calculate and record the R-values, and to predict whether the charged particle would remain stationary, whether it would move in a straight line, or performing a clockwise or anti-clockwise circular motion within the uniform magnetic field. In order pupils to predict the particle's rotation (clockwise/anti-clockwise) they were informed the three-finger rule of the right hand.

In Stage 4 of the activity, the pupils divided into groups of two (one with better performance in physics and another with moderate performance in

the same teaching subject) and they discussed-negotiated to exchange results, experiences, and findings, and made corrections whether it was proper. Also, they recorded on the worksheet their explanations of their corrections (why they made corrections?).

They were also given Table (2) and were asked to calculate the period, T for one rotation.

Table 1. Calculation of radius, R and prediction of particle motion.

a/a	Particle charge (q)	Initial velocity (m/s)	Radius of the circular orbit (m)	Particle motion
A1.1	+q (0 C)	0		
A1.2	+q (0 C)	2		
A1.3	+q(2μC)	0		
A1.4	+q(2μC)	2		
A1.5	+q(2μC)	4		
A1.6	-q(-2μC)	0		
A1.7	-q(-2μC)	2		
A1.8	-q(-2μC)	4		

Table 2. Calculation of period, T.

a/a	Particle charge, q(C)	Magnetic field, B(T)	Period, T(s)
A2.1	+q (0 C)	2	
A2.2	+q (0 C)	3	
A2.3	+q(q=2μC)	2	
A2.4	+q(q=2μC)	3	
A2.5	-q(-q=-2μC)	2	
A2.6	-q(-q=-2μC)	3	

In Stage 5 of the activity, the pupils experimented with the simulation and asked to choose the values of

B, q, v, adjust the particle start place, see the particle motion, and record the radius R, period T values and particle motion in corresponding Tables (1) and (2). They were also instructed that: when the particle is stationary, then $R = 0$, and when the particle moves straight, then, $R = \infty$ and $T = \infty$.

Figure (2) shows a snapshot of the simulated environment where the pupils experimented with. It identifies the changes in which pupils made the necessary choices as well as the circular motion of the charged particle within the uniform magnetic field.

Figure 2. Simulated environment where the pupils experimented with.

In Stage 6 of the activity, the pupils worked in groups to exchange results, experiences, and findings and to negotiate with them. Also, they were asked to explain the differences between their predictions and their final results and to record on the worksheet their explanations of their possible corrections (why they made corrections?).

In Stage 7 there was a discussion-examination about the cases of pair's : a) $v = 0$ and $q = 0$, b) $v = 0$ and $q = 0$, and c) $v = 0$ and $q = 0$ where the pupils were asked to use the equation (4) to prove whether in this case, the Lorentz force exerted on the particle.

In Stage 8 there was an extended discussion (through a guided dialogue with the instructor) on the last results of pupils. Also, they recorded on the worksheet their explanations of their new possible corrections (why did they make corrections?).

Great importance was given to how pupils accepted

the correct ideas of their peers through discussion and negotiation. Discussion between pupils and the instructor played a very important role in correcting pupils' misconceptions and learning difficulties through the structured guided dialogue that the instructor provided the pupils.

4. Results

For the data collection, became a systematic organization of the data to prevent from becoming overwhelmed by the amount of the results and to prevent us from losing sight of the original research purpose and questions. Data collection was mainly based on how the pupils correct their misconceptions and learning difficulties. Thus, the intention was to collect information about how the pupils processed new information.

The quantitative data were collected from the tables that completed by the pupils. The qualitative data were collected from the interpretation of pupils' explaining of the differences between the calculated values and the values they received from the simulation. Also, differences between their predictions of the particle motions and the corresponding motions they received from the simulation.

Moreover, strong qualitative data were collected from the results of the structured guided dialogues with pupils that have had difficulties in interpreting their results and they needed more support and guidance.

4.1. Quantitative Results

From the processing of the pupils' worksheets, the results presented in Tables (3) and (4), which are the pupils' success rates in the questions in Tables (1) and (2) before and after using the simulation.

The percent refers to pupils that answered correctly or incorrectly the questions in Tables (1) and (2). For example, in the case of A1.1 where the particle charge is $q = 0$ (uncharged) and the particle speed is $v = 0$ (stationary), the percentage of pupils that correctly calculating the radius value before using the simulation was 67 percent and after using the simulation it climbed to 83 percent.

4.2. Qualitative Results Obtained from the Interpretation of Pupils' Explanations

In this intervention was examined only the assessment of the efficacy of the strategy mentioned above comparing the pupil perceptions before and after the intervention.

From the examination of the samples given to the pupils to justify any changes in their perceptions, they were as follows:

When the pupils were asked to explain the differences and choose the correct entry between their prediction and that of simulation, most of them chose that of simulation and were able to explain their choice (but not with an absolute scientific way). Also, a small percentage of pupils insisted on their views without being able to explain them.

Table 3. Results of the radius calculation.

a/a	Before using the simulation(%)	After using the simulation(%)	p (two-tailed)
A1.1	67	83	0.6500
A1.2	0	58	0.0024
A1.3	83	92	0.8100
A1.4	75	100	0.5100
A1.5	75	100	0.5100
A1.6	92	100	0.8400
A1.7	50	100	0.1400
A1.8	50	92	0.2200

When the pupils were asked to collaborate in order to exchange experience and results, in three cases of collaboration we have had positive results, that is, these pupils were helped through the collaboration to correct their errors, in two cases of collaboration we had negative results, that is, these pupils, while before the collaboration they have had a proper value of their results, through collaboration they adopted the wrong value of their classmate. In seven cases of collaboration, there was no change.

Some pupils showed naive conceptions morphing

into a scientifically-acceptable concept. However, a couple of pupils changed from a scientifically-accepted conception into a naive conception. The discussion between pupils and the instructor showed that some pupils changed from a naive conception into a scientifically-accepted conception.

Table 4. Results of the period calculation.

a/a	Before using the simulation(%)	After using the simulation(%)	p (two-tailed)
A2.1	0	100	<0.0001
A2.2	0	100	<0.0001
A2.3	75	92	0.6500
A2.4	50	92	0.2200
A2.5	67	100	0.3700
A2.6	33	92	0.0544

Consequently, the negotiation between pupils helped some pupils correct their naive conception, but not all of them.

Thus, the structured guided dialogues were used to address misconceptions and learning difficulties of a small percentage of pupils.

4.3. Qualitative Results obtained from the Structured Guided Dialogues

In the below dialogues, the instructor used three ways of cognitive conflict, two from the mathematics (application of the formula and explanation of the formula's results) and one of the simulation with the aim of confronting misconceptions and learning difficulties of pupils. The conversation between instructor and pupil is very simple. The student responds to instructor's question with 'yes' or 'no' if he or she insists on his or her belief or no, respectively.

The examples below showing the effectiveness of the structured guided dialogue in confronting misconceptions created by the undefined forms and forms of infinite due to the formalism of electromagnetism.

Example 1

Instructor: No Lorentz force is exerted on the particle because in the equation $F_L = B \cdot v \cdot |q|$ either $v = 0$ or $q = 0$ or both of them are zero gives the Lorentz force total result zero. Therefore, since in these specific cases, no Lorentz force is exerted on the particle, then there is no circular motion. Consequently, the given pairs of values must be restrictions.

Instructor: Which is the value of the radius, R, of a charged particle with $q = 2 \mu\text{C}$ and mass, $m = 1\text{mg}$ (10^{-6} Kg) which it stays motionless ($v = 0\text{m/s}$) in a uniform magnetic field with a magnetic induction, $B = 2\text{T}$? (This question is intended to identify a common misconception that the pupils usually have about this section of electromagnetism. This misconception is that the magnetic poles exert forces on electric charges in the plane of the charge and magnet, regardless of whether the charge was moving or not).

Pupil A: Infinite radius, R.

Instructor: Applying to the equation:

$$R = \frac{m \cdot v}{B \cdot |q|}$$

the given values by Table (1) of the activity you've been working with, we have:

$$R = \frac{m \cdot v}{B \cdot |q|} = \frac{1 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 0}{2 \cdot |2 \cdot 10^{-6}|} = 0 \text{ m}$$

Therefore, the radius is not infinite, but zero. In the limitations we set at the beginning, this pair of parameter values ($v = 0$ and $q \neq 0$) also to belong and no Lorentz force is applied to the particle. Do you insist yet that the radius of the particle motion is infinite?

Pupil A: Yes.

Instructor: Generally, the value of a fraction is **infinite** if the numerator is zero and the denominator is zero or infinite. Thus, the value of the radius R is **infinite** if the numerator is not zero or infinite, and the denominator is zero. However, since the value of linear velocity, v is zero, then the numerator is zero. Also, B and q, are not zero, so the denominator is not zero. Consequently, the value of the radius, R, is not

infinite, but it is zero. Do you insist that the value of the particle motion is **infinite**?

Pupil A: Yes.

Instructor: During your study of simulation you might have concluded that the radius, R, of the circular motion, is **infinite** if the particle moves rectilinearly. In this case, the particle remains motionless. This means that the radius, R, of the circular motion, is zero (we have no revolution). Do you insist that the value of the particle motion is **infinite**?

Pupil A: No.

Example 2

Instructor: Which is the value of the radius, R, of an uncharged particle ($q = 0\mu\text{C}$) with mass, $m = 1\text{mg}$ (10^{-6} Kg) which it moves with $v = 10\text{m/s}$ in a uniform magnetic field with a magnetic induction, $B = 2\text{T}$? (This question is intended to identify a common misconception that the pupils usually have about this section of electromagnetism. This misconception is that the magnetic poles exert forces on neutral electric charges ($q = 0$) in the plane of the charge and magnet, regardless of whether the charge was moving or not).

Pupil B: undefined.

Instructor: Applying to the equation:

$$R = \frac{m \cdot v}{B \cdot |q|}$$

the given values by table 1 of the activity you have been working with, we have:

$$R = \frac{m \cdot v}{B \cdot |q|} = \frac{1 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 10}{2 \cdot 0} = \infty$$

Therefore, the radius is not undefined, but infinite. With the restrictions, this pair of parameter values ($v \neq 0$ and $q = 0$) also belongs and no Lorentz force is applied to the particle. Do you insist yet that the radius of the particle motion is **undefined**?

Pupil B: Yes.

Instructor: Generally, the value of a fraction is **undefined** if the numerator is zero (or infinite) and the denominator is zero (or infinite). Thus, the value of the radius R is **undefined** if the numerator is zero (or infinite), and the denominator is zero (or infinite). However, since the value of linear velocity, v is not zero, then the numerator is not zero, but the denominator is zero because q is zero. Consequently, the value of the radius, R, is not **undefined**, but it is infinite. Do you insist that the value of the particle motion is **undefined**?

Pupil B: Yes.

Instructor: During your study of simulation you might have concluded that the radius, R, of the circular motion, is **undefined** if we do not know its motion. In this case, the particle moves rectilinearly. This means that the radius, R, of the circular motion is infinite as we explained during the activity (a line is equal to a circle which has an infinite radius). Do you insist that the value of the particle motion is **undefined**?

Pupil B: No.

Example 3

Instructor: Which is the value of the radius, R, of an uncharged particle ($q = 0\mu\text{C}$) with mass, $m = 1\text{mg}$ (10^{-6} Kg) which it is immobile ($v = 0\text{m/s}$) in a uniform magnetic field with a magnetic induction, $B = 2\text{T}$? (This question is intended to identify a common misconception that the pupils usually have about this section of electromagnetism. This misconception is that the magnetic poles exert forces on neutral electric charges ($q=0$) in the plane of the charge and magnet, regardless of whether the charge was moving or not).

Pupil C: **undefined**.

Instructor's answer: According to mathematics, the value of a fraction is undefined if the numerator is zero (or infinite) and the denominator is zero (or infinite). Thus, the value of the radius R is **undefined** if the numerator is zero (or infinite), and the denominator is zero (or infinite). However, since the value of linear velocity, v is zero, then the numerator

is zero and the denominator is zero because q is zero. Consequently, the value of the radius, R, is really undefined, but in simulation, you see that the particle is immobile in a concrete position. This means that the radius R is not **undefined**, but it is zero. Do you insist that the value of the particle motion is **undefined**?

Pupil C: No.

Example 4

Instructor: Which is the value of the period T of the circular motion of the uncharged particle ($q = 0\mu\text{C}$) with mass, $m = 1\text{mg}$ (10^{-6} Kg) which it moves with $v = 10\text{m/s}$ in a uniform magnetic field with a magnetic induction, $B=2\text{T}$? (This question is intended to identify a common misconception that the pupils usually have about this section of electromagnetism.)

Pupil A: **undefined**.

Instructor's answer: Applying to the equation:

$$T = \frac{2\pi \cdot m}{B \cdot |q|}$$

the given values by table 1 of the activity you have been working with, we have:

$$T = \frac{2\pi \cdot m}{B \cdot |q|} = \frac{2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot 1 \cdot 10^{-6}}{2 \cdot 0} = \infty$$

Therefore, the period is not undefined, but it is infinite. This pair of parameter values ($v \neq 0$ and $q = 0$) also belongs to the restrictions and no Lorentz force is applied to the particle. Do you insist that the period of particle motion is undefined?

Pupil B: Yes.

Instructor's answer: Generally, the value of a fraction is **undefined** if the numerator is zero (or infinite) and the denominator is zero (or infinite). Thus, the value of the period T is **undefined** if the numerator is zero (or infinite), and the denominator is zero (or infinite). However, since the value of mass, m is not zero, then the numerator is not zero, but the denominator is zero because q is zero. Consequently, the value of the period, T, is not **undefined**, but it is infinite. Do you still insist that the value of the period of the particle

motion is **undefined**?

Pupil B: No.

An interesting case where encountered by the pupils, and the structured guided dialogue helped them in particular, is that for $v = 0$ and $q \neq 0$ ($q = 2\mu\text{C}$). If it will be applied on the formula for calculating the period, then it gives as result 1.57s. Of course, this is not correct since the particle is immobile.

5. Data analysis and Discussion

For the data analysis, the quantitative and qualitative data were coded. As methods of analysis the one sample t-test (two-tailed) between pupils' percents (quantitative), and conversation analysis (qualitative) were used.

In Stage 1 of the activity, the majority of pupils accepted that the two motions (moon's motion around the Earth and the charged particle's motion, at an initial constant speed, perpendicular to the direction of a uniform magnetic field) are governed by the same principles and therefore we can use the formulas of mechanics to calculate the radius and period of the circular movement of the charged particle.

In Stage 2 of the activity, the majority of pupils succeeded in compiling the given formulas and calculating the radius and the period formulas of the circular movement of the charged particle.

In Stages 3 and 4 of the activity, in cases, A1.2, A2.1, and A2.2 all of the pupils calculating values of the radius and period were incorrect and they due mainly to the **undefined** forms and forms of infinite.

In case A1.2, all the pupils have had difficulty in calculating the radius and period of particle's circular orbit, where $v \neq 0$ and $q = 0$, that is, when the numerator is not zero and the denominator is zero (infinite value).

In case of A1.1, where $v = 0$ and $q = 0$, most pupils recorded the radius as zero (67%) and only 33% of the pupils recorded that the radius was **undefined**. This misconception comes from mathematics, where pupils know that the zero by zero division is undefined. In physics, however, as in this case, the particle remains in the same position as long as the

Lorentz force does not apply to it. Therefore, the radius is zero and not **undefined**.

In case of A2.1, all the pupils had difficulty in calculating the period of particle's circular orbit, where $v = 0$ and $q = 0$, that is, when both the numerator and the denominator are zero (**undefined** value).

In Stages 5 and 6 of the activity, in cases of A2.1 and A2.2, we have had radical changes in the views of pupils where they strongly supported their results and findings because there was visualization and mathematical explanation of these cases and socio-cognitive conflicts might also be created through discussion and negotiation.

In cases where the simulation was very effective (helped significantly the pupils to correct their mistakes), because there was a significant difference between the samples, were A1.2 ($p = 0.0024$), A2.1 ($p < 0.0001$), and A2.2 ($p < 0.0001$). The case A2.6 can be considered as marginally significant.

In case of values of pair $v \neq 0$ and $q = 0$, when the radius and the period get an infinite value, no pupil gave a correct answer before using the simulation. After experimenting with the simulation, taking also into account the worksheet instructions, most of the pupils concluded that $R = \infty$ and $T = \infty$.

In case of values of pair $v = 0$ and $q \neq 0$, most of the pupils (83 percent), before experimenting with the simulation, concluded that $R = 0$, while after experimenting with the simulation, almost all pupils concluded that $R = 0$ (92 percent).

In cases of A1.4, A1.5, A1.6, and A1.7 the simulations were effective in confronting misconceptions or learning difficulties of all pupils and it is in line with McDermott's [31] conclusion that computer simulations have been proven effective in conceptual change in science.

In case of prediction of the clockwise or anti-clockwise rotation of the particle, 83 percent of the pupils correctly answered before the simulation, and 100 percent of the pupils correctly answered after the simulation.

As mentioned above, when the pupils were asked to explain the differences and choose the correct entry between their prediction and that of simulation, most of them chose that of simulation and were able to

explain their choice (but not with an absolute scientific way). Also, a small percentage of pupils insisted on their views without being able to explain them. Here we agree with Planinic et al. (2005) [23] research, that is, several intellectually less able pupils may fail to recognize the conflict and some of those who do recognize it might not be able to resolve it. Also verified the Limon's (2001) [22] view, that is, the success of the cognitive dissonance approach depends strongly on the ability of each pupil to recognize and resolve the conflict. In order to be faced this problem the guided dialogue was designed.

In cases of A2.1 and A2.2, we have radical changes in the views of pupils and they strongly supported their results and findings because we had visualization and mathematical explanation of these cases, and socio-cognitive conflicts might also be created through discussion and negotiation.

In Stage 7 of the activity, pupils were asked to set restrictions on using the formulas they calculated. After discussing with the researcher (author of this article), all pupils concluded that Lorentz's force is not exerted on the particle in cases of three pairs ($v = 0$ & $q = 0$, $v = 0$ & $q \neq 0$, and $v \neq 0$ & $q = 0$). After this conclusion, they were asked whether restrictions might be placed on using the formulas they used. After an extended discussion, the researcher summed up the views of the pupils and gave some further explanations. Finally, most of the pupils accepted that the formulas for calculating the radius and period should only be used if the Lorentz's force applied to the particle.

In Stage 8 of the activity, through the structured guided dialogue with the pupils who have learning difficulties the instructor (author of this article) gave the proper feedback and explanations and all pupils showed to accept the scientific views for all the cases.

6. Conclusions

From this intervention, the view of Flick & Bell (2000) [28] that the effectiveness of computer simulations is closely connected to the pedagogy through which they are employed as well as the view of Dilber and Duzgun (2008) [20], that is, when using analogical instruction, it is probably the simulations to cause much better perceptions of a

scientific conception and elimination of alternative conceptions may have been confirmed.

In general, McDermott (1990) [31] and Trundle and Bell (2010) [32] argument is confirmed, that is computer simulations have proved effective in conceptual change as well as computer simulations are effective in promoting cognitive dissonance and desirable conceptual changes.

This intervention considered that the only evaluation of the efficacy of the aforementioned strategy was to compare the pupil's ideas before and after the intervention. In most students, their naive perception was transformed into a scientifically-accepted perception. However, two pupils changed from a scientifically-accepted perception into a naive perception. Consequently, the negotiation between pupils helped some pupils correct their naive perception, but not all of them. The structured guided dialogs between pupils and the instructor has shown that they are quite effective since some pupils with learning difficulties changed from a naive perception to a scientifically-accepted perception. Consequently, the structured guided dialogues between instructor (or an intelligent system) and pupils are very important to address possible naive perceptions of pupils.

To sum up, it was confirmed the hypothesis that the use of analogies, simulations, guided discovery, explorations, communication, and structured guided dialogues facilitates pupils to address the following misconceptions and learning difficulties created by the formalism of electromagnetism.

- a) The pupils consider that the magnetic poles exert forces on electric charges in the plane of the charged particle and magnet, regardless of whether the charge was moving or not;
- b) A constant magnetic field changes the speed (magnitude of velocity) of a charged particle which moves in it;

As well as the following misconceptions and learning difficulties created by the formalism of electromagnetism:

- c) The pupils consider that the magnetic poles exert forces on neutral electric charges ($q = 0$) in the plane of the uncharged particle (e.g., neutrino) and magnet, regardless of whether the

charge was moving or not;

- d) Pupils have misconceptions and learning difficulties in cases of (a) $v = 0$ and $q = 0$, (b) $v = 0$ and $q \neq 0$, and (c) $v \neq 0$ and $q = 0$, when they calculate the radius and period of a particle's circular orbit (charged or neutral charged), when it moves or not, perpendicular to a uniform magnetic field;

It has also been confirmed that the proposed method helps pupils:

- e) calculate physics quantities and correctly use the rule of the three fingers of the right hand to predict the particle motion;
- f) comprehend their errors and to revise their views;
- g) be able to explain their choices, but not all of them;
- h) accept that formulas restrictions are required to avoid undefined and infinite forms.

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